

Body Mass Index and Hernia Size of >2 Cm Could Be the Risk Factors for Umbilical Hernia Recurrence: A Retrospective Study.Subhabrata Das¹, Pratibha Misra², Sukamal Das³, Jyotiranjana Mohapatra⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Surgery, S. L. N. Medical College and Hospital, Koraput, Odisha.²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, M. K. C. G. Medical College and Hospital, Berhampur, Odisha.³Assistant Professor, Department of ENT, Dharanidhar Medical College, Keonjhar, Odisha.⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Surgery, Shri Jagannath Medical College & Hospital, Puri, Odisha.

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Abstract:**Background:** Umbilical hernia has gained little attention from surgeons in comparison with other types of abdominal wall hernias (inguinal, postoperative); however, the primary suture for umbilical hernia is associated with a recurrence rate of 19–54%.**Aim and Objectives:** To analyze the results of the umbilical hernia repair and to assess the independent risk factors influencing umbilical hernia recurrence.**Materials and Methods:** A retrospective analysis of patients who underwent surgery for umbilical hernia in the Shri Jagannath Medical College and Hospital, Puri over a period of two years from January 2022 to December 2023. Age, sex, hospital stay, hernia size, patient's body mass index, and postoperative complications were analyzed. Postoperative evaluation included pain and discomfort in the abdomen and hernia recurrence rate. Hernia recurrence was diagnosed during the patients' visit to a surgeon. Two surgical methods were used to repair umbilical hernia: open suture repair technique (keel technique) and open mesh repair technique (only technique). Every operation was chosen individually by a surgeon.**Results:** A total 194 patients (62 males and 132 females) with umbilical hernia were examined. The mean age of the patients was 57.1±15.4 years, hernia anamnesis – 7.6±8.6 years, hospital stay – 5.38±3.8 days. One hundred eighty four patients (94.8%) were operated on using open suture repair technique and 10 (5.2%) patients – open mesh repair technique. Only 7% of patients whose BMI was >30 kg/m² and hernia size >2 cm and 4.3% of patients whose BMI was <30 kg/m² and hernia size <2 cm were operated on using onlay technique (P>0.05). The rate of postoperative complications was 5.2%. Sixty-seven patients (69%) answered the questionnaire. The complete patient's recovery time after surgery was 2.4±3.4 months. Twenty eight patients (20.9%) complained of pain or discomfort in the abdomen, and fourteen patients (10.4%) had ligature fistula after the surgery. Ninety patients (67.2%) did not have any complaints after surgery. The recurrence rate after umbilical hernia repair was 8.9%. The recurrence rate was higher when hernia size was >2 cm (9% for <2 cm vs 10.5% for >2 cm) and patient's BMI was >30 kg/m² (8.6% for < 30 vs 10.7% for >30). There were 10 recurrence cases after open suture repair and one case after onlay technique. One hundred twelve patients (83.6%) assessed their general condition after surgery as good, 18 patients (13.4%) as satisfactory, and only 4 patients (3%) as poor.**Conclusions:** We did not find any significant independent risk factors for umbilical hernia recurrence. However, based on reviewed literature, higher patient's body mass index and hernia size of >2 cm could be the risk factors for umbilical hernia recurrence.**Keywords:** Umbilical Hernia, Recurrence, Body mass index, Surgery.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Umbilical hernias, unlike inguinal or postoperative hernias, haven't received as much focus from surgeons. Research suggests traditional repair methods for umbilical hernias have high recurrence rates (19-54%). However using mesh during repair can significantly lower this risk. This study aimed to examine umbilical hernia repair outcomes and

identify independent risk factors influencing recurrence.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective analysis of patients who underwent surgery for umbilical hernia in Shri Jagannath Medical College and Hospital, Puri over a period of

two years from January 2022 to December 2023. Age, sex, hospital stay, hernia size, patient's body mass index (BMI), and postoperative complications were analyzed. Postoperative evaluation included pain and discomfort in the abdomen and hernia recurrence rate. The questionnaire, which involved all these previously mentioned topics, was sent to all patients by mail. Hernia recurrence was diagnosed during the patients' visit to a surgeon.

Umbilical hernias repaired using two different open techniques: suture repair (keel technique) and mesh repair (onlay technique). The choice of method depended on the surgeon's judgment. Researchers analyzed the data using descriptive statistics. They compared measurements between the two groups using the unpaired Student's t-test for normal data, the Mann-Whitney U test for non-normal data, and the chi-square test for categorical data. Additionally, logistic regression analysis was used to identify factors influencing hernia recurrence. All data were presented as averages (mean) and variability (standard deviation). A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study examined 194 patients (62 men and 132 women) with umbilical hernias. The average patient age was 57.1 years old (with a standard deviation of 15.4 years). The average duration of their hernia was 7.6 years (with a standard deviation of 8.6 years), and their average hospital stay was 5.4 days (with a standard deviation of 3.8 days).

Most patients (94.8%, or 184 people) underwent surgery using an open suture (keel) repair technique. Only a small number (5.2%, or 10 people) received open mesh (onlay) repair. Interestingly, body mass index (BMI) and hernia size didn't significantly influence the choice of repair method ($p > 0.05$). Details are shown in Figure 1.

A small portion of patients (5.2%) experienced complications after surgery. This included fluid buildup (seroma) in the wound area (2.1% of patients), blood collection (hematoma) in one patient (1%), and pus accumulation (suppuration) in two patients (2.1%).

Figure 1: The distribution of patients to different repair groups by hernia size and patients' body mass index.

Out of 134 patients (69%), those who completed a follow-up questionnaire were examined for hernia recurrence. The average recovery time was 2.4 months, with a variation of 3.4 months. Among the patients, 20.9% (28 patients) reported abdominal pain or discomfort after surgery. Additionally, 10.4% (14 patients) developed a ligature fistula. Fortunately, 67.2% (90 patients) experienced no complications following surgery. Our study also identified a recurrence rate of 8.9% (12 patients). While larger hernias (>2 cm) and higher BMI (>30 kg/m²) were associated with an increased chance of recurrence, this trend wasn't statistically significant. Our study observed 10 recurrences following open suture repair compared to just 1 after open mesh

repair. Additionally, a vast majority (83.6%) of the 112 patients rated their overall condition as good after surgery, with 13.4% rating it as satisfactory and only 3% as poor.

Discussion

Umbilical hernias, most frequent in people in their 50s and 60s [1-3], are very common in older adults (over 90%). They are especially likely to occur in obese individuals, particularly women, and in people with liver cirrhosis [1, 4, 5]. Our study reflects this trend, with an average patient age of 57.1 years and 68% being female.

Over time, various surgical techniques have been developed to repair umbilical hernias. Early methods relied on simply stitching the hernia closed (suture herniorrhaphy) or using techniques like the Mayo or keel repair. Unfortunately, these methods resulted in high recurrence rates, ranging from 19% to 54% (as shown in studies 3, 6-8). Thankfully, the introduction of mesh materials significantly lowered recurrence rates to around 15-20% (study 6). Further research by Arroyo et al. (study 2) demonstrated that using mesh during umbilical hernia repair could dramatically reduce recurrence rates to as low as 0.95%.

Our study, looking back at past patient records, found a surprisingly low overall recurrence rate of 8.9% across both open suture and open mesh repair groups. Due to the limited number of patients (only 5) who received mesh repair, we couldn't analyze or compare recurrence rates between the two groups. We suspect, however, that with a larger mesh repair sample size, the recurrence rate in this group might have been higher. This study did not delve into specific risk factors, but many other retrospective studies have explored these factors influencing umbilical hernia recurrence.

While limited research has identified risk factors for umbilical hernia recurrence, a well-designed study by Arroyo et al. (2000) found no link between hernia size and how likely it is to come back. This randomized controlled trial compared two surgical approaches: suturing the hernia closed versus using mesh reinforcement. Interestingly, the mesh repair group had a significantly lower recurrence rate (1%) compared to the suture repair group (11%).

Our study found no significant difference in recurrence rates based on whether the umbilical hernia was larger or smaller than 3 cm. However, a body mass index (BMI) greater than 30 kg/m² was identified as a risk factor for recurrence (1). Although our retrospective data showed a slightly higher recurrence rate in patients with both a larger hernia size (>2 cm) and higher BMI (>30 kg/m²) compared to those with smaller hernias and lower BMI, this difference wasn't statistically significant. Studies have shown that obese patients (BMI > 30 kg/m²) experience higher umbilical hernia recurrence rates after traditional repair methods. To address this, mesh repair with a tension-free technique is recommended for these patients [5]. A study by Halm et al. involving 131 patients found a recurrence rate of 13%, and interestingly, no link between wound infection and recurrence was observed [3].

In a study by Lau and Patil, researchers examined 102 patients with umbilical hernias. They compared different surgical techniques for repair, including Mayo repair, laparoscopic hernioplasty,

suture herniorrhaphy, and mesh hernioplasty. Interestingly, all patients received suture herniorrhaphy, and the study found a higher recurrence rate for hernias larger than 2 centimeters [7].

Using mesh for umbilical hernia repair can lead to wound complications like fluid buildup (seroma) or blood collection (hematoma) in 5.6% to 42% of cases [2,9]. While these complications can increase the risk of postoperative infection, pus formation (suppuration), and even hernia recurrence (2), a study by Abdel-Baki et al. found no link between mesh-related wound suppuration and recurrence. In this randomized study, 21 patients each received either mesh repair or traditional suture repair.

Doctors performed emergency surgery for umbilical hernias that became trapped (incarcerated). While the mesh repair technique increased the risk of wound infection after surgery, it also led to a 0% recurrence rate compared to a 19% recurrence rate with traditional suturing (p<0.05). This suggests mesh repair may be a better option despite the higher infection risk.

Emergency surgery for incarcerated umbilical hernias using mesh repair appears to be a safe and effective approach, with lower recurrence rates compared to traditional suturing [10]. Our retrospective study found a complication rate of 5.2%, similar to other studies. It's possible that a larger study with more mesh repairs might reveal a higher incidence of wound fluid buildup (seroma) or infection (suppuration).

The use of drains with mesh during umbilical hernia repair is debated. While some studies recommend it to prevent fluid buildup (seroma) or blood collection (hematoma) and wound infection (suppuration) [2, 6, 7], others advise against it due to the increased risk of infection in the mesh itself [6, 11].

Not every umbilical hernia needs mesh repair. The defect of <2 cm can be repaired successfully with suture herniorrhaphy or hernioplasty [3,7]. The suture repair technique for umbilical hernia is under tissue tension. This surgery technique increases the risk of recurrence and even increases the intraabdominal pressure after surgery [9]. An increase in intraabdominal pressure is associated with postoperative respiratory complications such as pneumonia and respiratory insufficiency. These complications can be one of the risk factors for hernia recurrence in long-term period. The mesh repair technique is a tension free surgery, which reduces postoperative respiratory complications and recurrence rate [9].

People with liver cirrhosis are more likely to develop umbilical hernias. While mesh repair is the preferred surgery for these patients, it can still

result in a recurrence rate of up to 13.6% [4]. Traditional open suture repair methods often lead to longer recovery times and lingering pain, with nearly 20% of patients experiencing discomfort even a year after surgery [9]. Tension-free mesh repair offers a faster path to recovery and a return to normal activity. Our study, looking back at patient data, showed that over 83% of patients rated their condition as good after surgery, with the remaining patients rating it satisfactory or poor. This held true for both open suture and open mesh repair techniques. Laparoscopic umbilical hernia repair, where surgeons operate through small incisions, appears to result in fewer complications like fluid buildup (seromas), blood collections (hematomas), infections, and other related issues compared to open repair surgery. Studies have shown recurrence rates of 8-10% in patients who undergo laparoscopic repair [12, 13].

Laparoscopic repair isn't necessary for all umbilical hernias. It's a more expensive procedure, and for smaller hernias (less than 2 cm), a traditional open repair is just as effective [13,14].

Conclusions

We did not find any significant independent risk factors for umbilical hernia recurrence. However, base on reviewed literature, higher patient's body mass index and hernia size of >2 cm could be the risk factors for umbilical hernia recurrence.

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References:

1. Arroyo A, Garcia P, Perez F, Andreu J, Candela F, Calpena R. Randomized clinical trial comparing suture and mesh repair of umbilical hernia in adults. *Br J Sur.* 2001; 88:1321-3.
2. Arroyo Sebastián A, Pérez F, Serrano P, Costa D, Oliver I, Ferrer R, et al. Is prosthetic umbilical hernia repair bound to replace primary herniorrhaphy in the adult patients? *Hernia.* 2002;6(4):175-7.
3. Halm JA, Heisterkamp J, Veen HF, Weidema WF. Long-term follow-up umbilical hernia repair: are there risk factors for recurrence after simple and mesh repair. *Hernia* 2005;9(4):334-7.
4. Mark D, Pescovitz MD. Umbilical hernia repair in patients with cirrhosis. *Ann Surg* 1984; 199(3):325-7.
5. Rodríguez-Hermosa JI, Codina-Cazador A, Ruiz-Feliú B, Roig-García J, Albiol-Quer M, Planellas-Giné P. Incarcerated umbilical hernia in a super-super-obese patient. *Obes Surg* 2008; 18(7):893-5.
6. Balique JG, Benchetrit S, Bouillot JL, Flament JB, Gouillat C, Jarsaillon P, et al. Intraperitoneal treatment of incisional and umbilical hernias using an innovative composite mesh: four-year results of a prospective multicenter clinical trial. *Hernia* 2005;9(1):68-74.
7. Lau H, Patil NG. Umbilical hernia in adults. *Surg Endosc* 2003;17(12):2016-20.
8. Carbajo MA, Martín del Olmo JC, Blanco JI, de la Cuesta C, Toledano M, Martín F, et al. Laparoscopic treatment vs. open surgery in the solution of major incisional and abdominal wall hernias with mesh. *Surg Endosc* 1999;13(3):250-2.
9. Venclauskas L, Šilanskaitė J, Kanišauskaitė J, Kiudelis M. Long-term results of incisional hernia treatment. *Medicina (Kaunas)* 2007;43(11): 855-60.
10. Abdel-Baki NA, Bessa SS, Abdel-razek AH. Comparison of prosthetic mesh repair and tissue repair in the emergency management of incarcerated para-umbilical hernia: a prospective randomized study. *Hernia* 2007;11(2):163-7.
11. Jamal MM. Umbilical hernia repair in children is pressure dressing necessary. *Pediatr Surg Int* 2006; 22:446-8.
12. Toy FK, Bailey RW, Carey S, Chappuis CW, Gagner M, Josephs LG, et al. Prospective, multicenter study of laparoscopic ventral hernioplasty. *Surg Endosc* 1998; 12:955-9.
13. Carbajo MA, del Olmo JC, Blanco JI, de la Cuesta C, Martín F, Toledano M, et al. Laparoscopic treatment of ventral abdominal wall hernias: preliminary results in 100 patients. *JLS.* 2000; 4:141-5.
14. Venclauskas L, Silanskaite J, Kiudelis M. Umbilical hernia: factors indicative of recurrence. *Medicina (Kaunas).* 2008;44(11):855-9.